

The model of "intelligent plant cultivating garden" (IPG) and its role in handling the crisis of "water, soil, and air"

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Abstract

The model of "intelligent plant cultivating garden" (IPG) is a device that handles and manages irrigation, heat degree, ventilation, and the degree of defusing fertilizer and toxicity through a programmable processor. By measuring and receiving basic data in a period of cultivating a certain product and by means of powerful electronic sensors and programming the electronic processor, the IPG can intelligently control the degree of irrigation in due times, heat, fertilizer, and toxicity. It can also prevent huge waste of water and overuse of fertilizer and toxicity. The IPG, which is being developed and examined in the Gilan Science and Technology Park for the time being, has a closed irrigation system. The volume of water which has been used once for the irrigation of the plant will be used again after filtration and enrichment. It is obvious that if used widely and in various climates, The IPG can have an incredible impact on fighting against drought and controlling the environmental pollutants. The IPG can also provide the condition of growth in the reservoir and eliminate time and place condition in cultivating and planting a product. It means that we can cultivate a certain product, whether in summer or in winter, whether in mountainous area or in a desert, without infusing excessive fertilizer and toxicity to the environment.

Keywords: intelligent plant cultivating garden, hydroponic, programmable processor, the Guilan Science and Technology Park, environmental pollutants

Introduction

Natural ecosystems and their procedures are not occasionally in a situation as we desire or do not meet our needs and, moreover, they are most of the times uncontrollable and very slow (Jafarniya, 1989). One of the methods of befitting and controlling these procedures is to draw on engineering technology, provided that all principles of work and the right use of mechanization are being observed (Rathore, 2005). Mechanization overcomes the natural forces and enhances our power in controlling the nature and environment in order that we can change it to our own benefit; on the other hand, mechanization fights against drought crisis and prevents biological damages to the environment. In two recent decades, a lot of endeavors have been made to use machinery in agriculture in Iran (Khoshgoftarmanish, 1989). Yet one of the main reasons of not keeping on using such machineries is the problem of using them regardless to place and time. On the whole, the main difference between mechanized cultivation and the traditional one lies in how cultivation and harvesting are carried out. In mechanized system, technology and engineering principles substitute man's labor, but the purpose of mechanized agriculture is even more than this. Its purpose is to decrease the use of water, to ease the hardship of the work, to overcome the difficulties of condition of the place under cultivation. Furthermore, mechanized agriculture tries to regulate the time and quantity of injecting and spreading anti-pests, to use proper fertilizer to enrich the soil and to cure its deficiency (Khoshgoftarmanish, 2007).

Mechanized agriculture can be used to meet the needs of the plants in such a way that the density and the health of the bushes in the surface level are observed. On one hand, the work will be done faster and more carefully and, on the other hand, we have succeeded to protect the environment and fight against

drought crisis through following grand management. By controlling and overcoming the mentioned problems, IPG makes it possible by means of electronic system for everybody with any knowledge and any place on the earth and any time they wish to cultivate their needed products without any damage and to use it commonly (Papado, 2000). This method is valuable and its importance stands out while having a drought because it saves a lot of water and energy. Here it must be mentioned proudly that this model has succeeded to receive a prize in Iran international Research and Development festival (R&D).

How the system works

General function: in this type of cultivation, garden is managed intelligently by an electronic system, which is under construction and is being tested. ATMEGA32, which is programmable, receives its data from SHT sensor once every minute, and according to its given instruction, it processes them, and then controls the electrical taps for irrigation, heaters for heat, ventilators for ventilation, the valves for opening and closing etc. The machine has a digital monitor which shows all the mentioned procedures and reminds the user the necessary procedures (Rathore, 2005). Encountering any malfunction and abnormality, the machine runs the alarm and shows the faults, for example lack of water, on the monitor.

The irrigation system: The irrigation system of this machine is completely a closed one. Water, after irrigation and being pumped upon seed tray, will be drained from the below and then will be sent up to the top reservoir section to be enriched and purified. After enrichment and purification, the water will be filled again into reservoir. It should be mentioned that this operation not only will make the irrigation easier_ no need to dig canals _it also prevents the waste of water on the farm to a great degree. In fact, the most portion of the decrease of water in the reservoir happens because of the feeding of the plants and surface evaporation. When we compare these two systems in how much water they use, especially when the soil is thirsty, we understand that the modern one is quite incomparable and much better. Moreover, this system is a treasure for farm where wells or canals have to be dug and used (Arshadi, 2007).

Figure 1. The irrigation system

Heat Control: the heating system of this machine begins to work by turning on the improvised heater after the sensor measures the temperature of the reservoir and finds out that it differs too much with the outside temperature. Cooling system is the very ventilating system inside the reservoir, working while the processor signals the ventilators should be turned on. In order to control diseases and to asperse the poison, some nozzles have been improvised in the reservoir and they begin to spray the poison over the seeds and sprouts at the proper and set time. (Arshadi, 2007)

Controlling the PH of the soil: a digital PH indicator is used in the seed tray in order to measure the PH of the soil and to send the data to the microprocessor which analyzes them. According to programmed condition, it tries to reach the PH of the soil to the normal level (Al Harbi, 1994). The normalization of the PH takes place in the insemination shown in picture 2-2-1 through irrigation system.

Earthworm: In this project, after many trials and mistakes and pedological studies, it was decided to use earthworms in the soil of seed tray (Khoshgoftarmansh, 2010). Because the designed room in "intelligent plant cultivating garden" is like aquarium, it creates a suitable place for the cultivation and growth of the plant. The earthworms find a suitable bed for living in this artificial environment. This increases the

weight of products considerably (Mobli, 2011). Therefore, we can take advantages of natural earthworms which make ducts among the roots and holes on the cultivation tray. It also makes us come closer to our three main goals.

1. Carrying oxygen to the roots
2. Helping to drain the still water in the tray
3. Preventing the damage to roots (Papado, 2000)

The results of cultivation, taking into consideration the item of water: The tables 1 and 2 show the essential application of one item (i.e. water) of the machine in comparison to traditional method. If we compare the figures of 1 and 2 with each other, we easily come to this conclusion that in cultivating vegetable in a twenty- day process in "intelligent plant cultivating garden" in 58sqm land of under cultivation only 32 liters of water has been used and the average of used water is 82.5 percent (Alizadeh,1930).

While in 35-day cultivation in traditional method, 1023 liter of water has been used and the products are not so good and satisfactory (Choudhary,1995). This result which is repeated in four times of tentative cultivation proves that the use of the machine is much better.

Table 1. 20day culture with Coriander

water efficiency (%)	water balance (lit)	water (lit)	the water (lit)	the culture of the area (m ²)	The following aspects of the culture	row
70	7	3	10	2	2x1	1
77.5	31	9	40	8	4x2	2
90	72	8	80	16	4x4	3
92.5	148	12	160	32	8x4	4
82.5	Average	32	290	58	sum	5

Table 2. Coriander 35 days cultivation in the traditional way

Water efficiency (%)	Water balance (lit)	Water (lit)	The water (lit)	the culture of the area (m ²)	The following aspects of the culture	row
1.3	2	148	150	2	2x1	1
3.4	7	203	210	8	4x2	2
2.2	8	342	350	16	4x4	3
1.8	10	530	540	32	8x4	4
2.175	Average	1023	1250	58	Sum	5

The following tables show the undisputable preference of item of water used by the machine. While water has been used 40 times more in the same volume of land under cultivation in traditional method. The 2.175 average shows how unsatisfactory the traditional method is and it shows its poor profitability. Later, concentrating on how much fertilizer and anti-pest has been used, the results of cultivation have been studied and compared between two samples of traditional cultivation and SGC cultivation.

The result of cultivation, examining the item of fertilizer and anti-pest: If we study the 3 and 4 tables carefully, we will find out that how much less fertilizer and anti-pest are used for 58sqm machine cultivation, at the same time, in comparison to traditional method, the quality of products is far much better.

Table 3. 20day culture with Coriander

Fertiliser (kg)	Pesticides (lit)	the culture of the area (m ²)	The following aspects of the culture	row
0.2	0.2	2	2x1	1
0.5	0.6	8	4x2	2
1.8	0.8	16	4x4	3
1.5	1.25	32	8x4	4
3	2.85	58	sum	5

Table 4. Coriander 35 days cultivation in the traditional way

Fertiliser (kg)	Pesticides (lit)	the culture of the area (m ²)	The following aspects of the culture	row
0.6	0.5	2	2x1	1
1.15	0.9	8	4x2	2
2.5	1.5	16	4x4	3
5.5	3.8	32	8x4	4
9.75	6.7	58	sum	5

Conclusion

If we want to make the comparisons in higher levels to the traditional cultivation with no reservoir, the result of this comparison will be quite clear. As a result, the impact of the wide-scale use of these machines can be regarded as a national plan which can offer proper approaches to fighting against the crisis, controlling the pollutant of environment, and starting a profitable business, as well (Mobli, 2011). It can also give a big hand to our independence and public welfare, besides having the following advantages:

1. Stopping the waste of energy
2. Preventing the spread of poisons in the environment.

Of course, there are far more advantages in the use of this machine, such as: creating a lot of jobs both in making and providing their accessories and side products after sale; innovating in the process of development of the machine; having outstanding effect upon the health of the environment; campaigning against drought crisis; providing self-sufficiency for every family, province and the country; decreasing noticeably the cost of transportation, etc.

It should be mentioned that the use of "intelligent plant cultivating garden" completely eliminates the irregular evaporation and the unwanted absorption of the water in the route of irrigation to farm. The hardship of conveying water to the farm (digging wells, making canals, local struggles and fights for using the rivers and streams, etc.) has been one of the farmers' perpetual worries.

References

- Al Harbi AR, Al-Omram AM, Wahdan H, Shalaby AA, 1994. Arid soil research and rehabilitation. Journal-article.
- Alizadeh M and Mohammadi S, 1930. An abridgement of main points in academic books and pamphlets from universities all over the country.
- Arshadi M, 2007. Hydroponic cultivation, project the undergraduate student, University of Guilan.
- Choudhary MI, Shalaby AA, Al-Omran AM, 1995. Water holding capacity and evaporation of calcareous soil Science And Plant Analysis.
- Jafarniya S, Da'ee M, Roberto K, SafaeeKhoram M, 1989. The Design of Hydroponic Cultivation System, Tehran.
- Khoshgoftarmanish A, 1989. The investigation of nourishing condition of plant and the management of fertilizer. The center of Isfahan industrial University Publication, Isfahan.
- Khoshgoftarmanish A, 2010. The advanced debates of nourishing the plants. The center of Isfahan industrial University Publication, Isfahan.
- Khoshgoftarmanish A, 2007. The principles of plant nourishment. Isfahan industrial University Publication Center, Isfahan.
- Mobli M, 2011. Greenhouse vegetable growing technology (soil and soilless culture).
- Papado P, 2000. Growing greenhouse seedless cucumber and greenhouse tomatoes in soil and in soilless Media.
- Rathore PS, 2005. Techniques and management of field crop production.